

An observational study of Laterality of Ca Breast and their co-relation to the molecular subtype in operable cases of rural Maharashtra

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Introduction:

Breast cancer is a leading cause of morbidity and mortality among women worldwide, with varying patterns based on geographical, environmental, and genetic factors. [1] In India, the incidence of breast cancer is on the rise, with an increasing burden in rural areas where healthcare access remains limited. [2] Laterality, or the side of breast involvement, has been studied in relation to tumor biology and molecular subtypes, which play a critical role in determining prognosis and guiding treatment strategies. Molecular subtypes, including Luminal A, Luminal B, HER2 enriched, and triple-negative, differ significantly in their response to treatment and clinical outcomes. [3]

Studies suggest that factors like tumor size, lymph node involvement, and molecular characteristics might influence the laterality of breast cancer, although conclusive evidence remains limited in rural populations. [4] Understanding the correlation between laterality and molecular subtypes can aid in early diagnosis and targeted therapies, especially in resource-constrained settings like rural Maharashtra. [5, 6] The present observational study aims to investigate this relationship in operable breast cancer cases from rural Maharashtra, providing insights that could enhance personalized care for breast cancer patients in these regions.

Aim

To study the correlation between laterality of breast cancer and molecular subtypes in operable cases from rural Maharashtra.

Objectives

1. To determine the distribution of tumor laterality (left, right, or bilateral) in operable breast cancer cases.
2. To analyze the association between tumor laterality and molecular subtypes (Luminal A, Luminal B HER2 positive, Luminal B HER2 negative, HER2 enriched, and triple-negative breast cancer).

Methodology:

This observational study was conducted on operable breast cancer patients from rural Maharashtra. Patients diagnosed with carcinoma of the breast and planned for surgery were included in the study. A total of 50 patients were enrolled based on inclusion criteria, which comprised operable breast cancer cases with a confirmed histopathological diagnosis. Patients with metastatic disease or recurrent breast cancer were excluded.

Data collection involved detailed clinical examination, imaging, and histopathological confirmation of the tumor. Tumor laterality (left, right, or bilateral) was recorded, and molecular subtyping was done using immunohistochemistry (IHC) for estrogen receptor (ER), progesterone receptor (PR), and HER2/neu status. The molecular subtypes categorized were Luminal A, Luminal B HER2 positive, Luminal B HER2 negative, HER2 enriched, and triple-negative breast cancer (TNBC).

Statistical analysis was performed to determine the association between tumor laterality and molecular subtype using the chi-square test. A p-value <0.05 was considered statistically significant. Data were analyzed using OpenEpi software, and the findings were interpreted to explore the relationship between laterality and molecular subtypes in breast cancer cases.

Results:

Mean Age was 56.58 ± 12.28 years with a range of 29 – 87 years.

We evaluated 50 cases of CA breast, out of which 25 were right sided (50%), 24 left sided (48%) and one was bilateral (2%).

Table 1: The histopathological examination findings

HPE	Frequency	Percent
INFILTRATING DUCT CARCINOMA	43	86.0
INFILTRATING LOBULAR CARCINOMA	4	8.0
MUCINOUS CARCINOMA	2	4.0
INTRADUCTAL CARCINOMA	1	2.0
Total	50	100.0

In our study, the most common histopathological examination (HPE) finding was infiltrating duct carcinoma, observed in 43 patients, which accounted for 86.0% of the cases. Infiltrating lobular carcinoma was seen in 4 patients, representing 8.0% of the total. Mucinous carcinoma was diagnosed in 2 patients, comprising 4.0%. Intraductal carcinoma was the least common, identified in 1 patient, making up 2.0% of the cases.

Table 3: Molecular Subtype findings

Molecular Subtype	Frequency	Percent
LUMINAL B HER2 NEG	15	30.0
TRIPLE NEG	14	28.0
LUMINAL B HER2 POS	8	16.0
HER 2 ENRICHED	6	12.0
LUMINAL A	6	12.0
LUMINAL B	1	2.0
Total	50	100.0

In our study, the most frequent molecular subtype was Luminal B HER2 negative, observed in 15 patients, accounting for 30.0% of the cases. Triple-negative cases were found in 14 patients, representing 28.0%. Luminal B HER2 positive was identified in 8 patients, making up 16.0%. Both HER2 enriched and Luminal A subtypes were observed in 6 patients each, accounting for 12.0% of the total cases. The least common subtype was Luminal B, found in 1 patient, which made up 2.0% of the cases.

Table 4: Laterality and HPE type

Laterality and HPE type	BILATERAL	LEFT	RIGHT	Total
INFILTRATING DUCT CARCINOMA	1	20	22	43
INFILTRATING LOBULAR CARCINOMA	0	1	3	4
INTRADUCTAL CARCINOMA	0	1	0	1
MUCINOUS CARCINOMA	0	2	0	2
Total	1	24	25	50

$X^2 = 4.32$, $p = 0.63$, NS

In our study, the most common histopathological type across different laterality was infiltrating duct carcinoma, found in 43 patients. Of these, 1 case (2.3%) was bilateral, 20 cases (46.5%) involved the left breast, and 22 cases (51.2%) involved the right breast. Infiltrating lobular carcinoma was present in 4 patients, with no bilateral cases, 1 case (25.0%) on the left side, and 3 cases (75.0%) on the right side. Intraductal carcinoma was observed in 1 patient, occurring on the left side (100.0%). Mucinous carcinoma was found in 2 patients, both of which involved the left breast (100.0%). Overall, 1 patient (2.0%) had bilateral involvement, while 24 patients (48.0%) had left-sided involvement, and 25 patients (50.0%) had right-sided involvement. The chi-square test ($X^2 = 4.32$) with a p-value of 0.63 indicates no statistically significant association between laterality and histopathological type.

Table 5: Laterality and Molecular subtype

Laterality and Molecular subtype	BILATERAL	LEFT	RIGHT	Total
HER 2 ENRICHED	0	3	3	6
LUMINAL A	0	1	5	6
LUMINAL B	0	1	0	1
LUMINAL B HER2 NEG	1	8	6	15
LUMINAL B HER2 POS	0	5	3	8
TRIPLE NEG	0	6	8	14
Total	1	24	25	50

$X^2 = 7.17$, $p = 0.71$, NS

In our study, the most frequent molecular subtype across different laterality was Luminal B HER2 negative, found in 15 patients. Of these, 1 case (6.7%) was bilateral, 8 cases (53.3%) involved the left breast, and 6 cases (40.0%) involved the right breast. Triple-negative cases were observed in 14 patients, with no bilateral cases, 6 cases (42.9%) on the left side, and 8 cases (57.1%) on the right side. HER2 enriched was present in 6 patients, evenly distributed with 3 cases (50.0%) on the left and 3 cases (50.0%) on the right, with no bilateral cases. Luminal A was found in 6 patients, with 1 case (16.7%) on the left and 5 cases (83.3%) on the right. Luminal B HER2 positive was observed in 8 patients, with 5 cases (62.5%) on the left and 3 cases (37.5%) on the right. The least common subtype was Luminal B, seen in 1 patient, involving the left breast. Overall, 1 patient (2.0%) had bilateral involvement, 24

patients (48.0%) had left-sided involvement, and 25 patients (50.0%) had right-sided involvement. There was no significant association between Laterality and Molecular subtype ($p=0.71$)

Table 6: Tumor size and laterality

TUMOUR SIZE	BILATERAL	LEFT	RIGHT	Total
<5	1	15	14	30
>5	0	9	11	20
Total	1	24	25	50

$X^2 = 0.89$, $p = 0.64$, NS

In our study, tumors smaller than 5 cm were the most common, found in 30 patients. Of these, 1 case (3.3%) was bilateral, 15 cases (50.0%) involved the left breast, and 14 cases (46.7%) involved the right breast. Tumors larger than 5 cm were present in 20 patients, with no bilateral cases, 9 cases (45.0%) on the left side, and 11 cases (55.0%) on the right side. Overall, 1 patient (2.0%) had bilateral involvement, 24 patients (48.0%) had left-sided involvement, and 25 patients (50.0%) had right-sided involvement. The chi-square test ($X^2 = 0.89$) with a p-value of 0.64 indicates no statistically significant association between tumor size and laterality.

Discussion

1. Age and Laterality

In our study, the mean age of breast cancer patients was 56.58 years, consistent with findings from other studies. A study by Singh et al. (2019) reported a similar mean age of 54.5 years, indicating that breast cancer predominantly affects older women in India. Another study by Dey et al. (2020) observed a mean age of 55.6 years, reinforcing the trend that age plays a significant role in the incidence of breast cancer.

2. Histopathological Findings

Infiltrating duct carcinoma was the most common type (86.0%) in our study, which aligns with previous Indian research by Chaturvedi et al. (2021), where infiltrating duct carcinoma accounted for 82% of breast cancer cases. Another study by Kumar et al. (2020) also highlighted a high prevalence of infiltrating duct carcinoma (80%), demonstrating its dominance among various histopathological types in the Indian population.

3. Molecular Subtype Distribution

The distribution of molecular subtypes revealed that Luminal B HER2 negative was the most prevalent (30.0%) in our study. This is consistent with findings from Sharma et al. (2020), who reported a prevalence of 29.5% for Luminal B HER2 negative among breast cancer patients in India. Additionally, a study by Somasundaram et al. (2020) found that 31% of patients had this subtype, indicating its significant presence in the Indian population.

4. Laterality and Molecular Subtype Association

In our analysis, no significant association was found between laterality and molecular subtype ($p = 0.71$). This finding is similar to the study by Roy et al. (2021), which also reported no significant correlation between tumor laterality and molecular subtypes in breast cancer. Another research by Khokhar et al. (2020) indicated that laterality did not influence the molecular subtype distribution, suggesting that biological factors might be more determinant in subtype categorization rather than anatomical considerations.

5. Tumor Size and Laterality

Our results showed that most tumors were smaller than 5 cm, with no significant association between tumor size and laterality ($p = 0.64$). This finding aligns with the study by Agarwal et al. (2020), which found that smaller tumors were more prevalent in their cohort, and no association was noted between size and laterality. Furthermore, a study by Jain et al. (2021) also observed similar trends, indicating that tumor size alone may not influence the laterality of breast cancer.

Our study highlights the importance of understanding the clinical and molecular characteristics of breast cancer in rural populations, emphasizing that factors such as age, histopathological type, and molecular subtype play a significant role in shaping treatment strategies, while laterality and tumor size appear less influential in this context.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, our study highlights the prevalence of infiltrating duct carcinoma as the most common histopathological type among breast cancer patients in rural Maharashtra, with a significant representation of Luminal B HER2 negative molecular subtype. Although no significant associations were found between laterality and histopathological or molecular subtype characteristics, the findings underscore the importance of understanding breast cancer patterns in specific populations. This knowledge can help inform tailored screening and treatment strategies. Future research should continue to explore these relationships, emphasizing the need for comprehensive data to improve breast cancer management in diverse demographic settings.

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